

TEACHING MULTILINGUALISM: LEARNING STRATEGIES

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8A Abay avenue, Almaty***Abstract**

The standards for the process of teaching foreign languages are changing as a result of the implementation of the Bologna Agreements. Today's foreign language teacher must not only give pupils with information, abilities, and form skills, but also help them build the capacity to independently study a foreign language and culture. It is very important to consider the construction and growth of students' independent educational competency, as well as acceptable methods of gaining knowledge and creating skills. The development of a student's ability to engage in independent educational and cognitive activity is dependent on the use of educational strategies. This essay investigates the qualities of a successful learner and argues for the importance of teaching strategies for acquiring a foreign language.

The same strategies are employed while learning a second foreign language as when learning the first, yet each has its own uniqueness. The deployment of any educational and cognitive procedures is distinguished by their awareness.

The distinctiveness of strategies for acquiring second and subsequent foreign languages is dictated by students' educational and linguistic background, as well as their age. The purpose of this article is to investigate the methods required for the development of the phonetic side of speech.

Keywords: multilingualism, educational autonomy, educational strategies, successful language learner, phonetic side of speech.

The ability to process large amounts of information quickly and efficiently is a time requirement and depends on the formation of the student's learning strategies. In relation to the acquisition of a foreign language, strategies are "combinations of intellectual techniques and efforts that are used by students to understand, memorize and use knowledge about the language system and speech skills and abilities; cognitive operations that are selected by students from among the possible ones to solve a communicative task." (Azimov E. G., Shchukin A. N., 2009)

In order to find out the reasons for success in mastering a foreign language, a "successful learner" and his or her learning behavior were characterized. H. Stern and J. Rubin distinguish the following characteristics of a "successful student": 1) lack of fear of making a mistake; 2) search for formal patterns and schemes; 3) experiments on the way to the goal; 4) attention to meaning; 5) readiness for exercise; 6) readiness to participate in real communication; 7) self-observation. H. Stern, in addition, names three more signs mentioned J. Rubin has implicitly: 8) discovering your own style in teaching; 9) active position and responsibility; 10) gradual development of the target language system independent of the native language.

The use of certain strategies depends on each individual, on his cognitive style. There are visual, auditory, communicative, motor, practice-oriented, abstract-analytical types. There are other classifications of learning styles, among which, in relation to the process of teaching a foreign language, one can note such cognitive styles as "utility-dependent – field-independent" (a tendency to global or analytical comprehension

of reality), "reflexive - impulsive" (a way of making decisions in complex problem tasks), etc. Already at school age, students know how they better understand, memorize, and assimilate the material. However, even students are not always aware of their individual cognitive style, its advantages and disadvantages, and the fact that the strategies they use depend on the cognitive style. By introducing students to new techniques, expanding their strategic repertoire, the teacher gives them the opportunity to choose for themselves more suitable and effective ways of teaching.

The necessity and importance of teaching students effective language acquisition strategies is based on the following provisions:

- mentally active students are more successful in learning: students who consciously organize and integrate new information into information already stored in the memory have more cognitive connections that support understanding and reproduction than those whose learning activity consists in memorizing;
- strategies can be learned. Students who know strategies and have the ability to apply them are more successful;
- learning strategies can be extended and transferred to other activities;
- learning foreign languages in academic conditions with the help of educational strategies will be more effective, since it has a lot in common with solving a problem situation in the native language.

The learned strategies can be transferred to the process of mastering a new foreign language (Rampillon, U., 2003):

- "smart guessing": assumes knowledge about the world, about the target language, about the context,

about interlanguage knowledge (the influence of native and foreign languages);

- hypothesis testing: 1) perception of the problem; 2) reflection; 3) hypothesis formulation; 4) hypothesis formulation; 5) hypothesis testing;
- integration of new knowledge into existing knowledge;
- parallel use of various sources of information and educational materials;
- mnemonic strategies for memorization;
- the use of words of native and learned foreign languages;
- word conversion of familiar languages;
- perception and use of kinship of languages;
- application of metalanguage terminology, etc.

The use of strategies should be done consciously. It is also necessary to inform students that educational strategies are applicable to the study of any foreign language, regardless of whether it is the first, second or third foreign language for students.

However, in order to use strategies when mastering a new language, it is necessary to master the minimum profile of strategies at the stage of mastering the first foreign language.

There are many classifications of strategies. The most famous classification of strategies belongs to R. Oxford, and includes the following strategies:

- direct strategies for learning a foreign language (mnemonic strategies, cognitive strategies, compensatory strategies);
- indirect strategies for learning a foreign language (metacognitive strategies, affective learning strategies, social strategies).

J. M. O'Malley and A. U. Chamot subdivide strategies into cognitive, metacognitive and socioaffective, thereby increasing the number of strategy groups compared to the previous classification (1990).

According to S. I. Lebedinsky and L. F. Herbig, an extensive classification containing two large groups of strategies (2011):

1) foreign language acquisition strategies (metacognitive, cognitive, socio-affective and pragmatic, communicative strategies);

2) strategies for using a foreign language.

Focusing on the strategies necessary for the development of the phonetic side of speech, we use the classifications presented above and consider three groups of strategies for teaching phonetics, namely metacognitive, cognitive and socio-affective strategies.

Metacognitive strategies are important for independent work. They are focused on awareness of what the learner is doing, what strategies he uses, as well as knowledge of the process of language acquisition and its individual links, including awareness of the ultimate goal of language learning in terms of achieving a certain level of speech development for students.

Metacognitive strategies for mastering the phonetic aspect of speech include the following:

- setting and achieving a goal;
- correlation of the goal with the results achieved;
- identification and discussion with the teacher of the most effective learning strategies and techniques;

- maintaining a positive attitude to the process of mastering the pronunciation side of speech;
- pronunciation assessment.

Cognitive strategies involve interaction with the studied material, manipulation of it, the use of special techniques, techniques for learning (Shchepilova A.V., 2005).

The following actions can be distinguished as cognitive strategies involving memorization and manipulation of the structures of the language being studied:

- recognize and repeat the stress in a word;
- recognize and repeat intonation;
- focus on the pronunciation of perceived speech (listening texts);
- record and listen to your voice;
- *establish analogies and formulate rules for understanding the relationship between sounds and letters;*
- *to identify the contrast between the phonetic phenomena of the studied language and the native / learned languages;*
- imitate the pronunciation / intonation of native speakers;
- memorize interesting oral texts (songs, poems, tongue twisters, etc.) and repeat them aloud or to yourself;
- humming lyrics, imitating intonation;
- associate words by phonetic similarity;
- use the sound in oral speech, using the words containing this sound.

Italicized strategies become the most relevant when mastering the second and subsequent foreign languages.

Socioaffective strategies involve interaction with other students, emotional involvement in the learning process. They are associated with collective learning activities, with obtaining information from native speakers, with the creation of an educational algorithm of action for the teacher, taking into account the capabilities and psychological characteristics of the student (Serebrantseva O.G., 2006). These include actions such as:

- watch movies and TV programs with subtitles;
- use the means of communication available to the student that contain audio information, such as the Internet, television, radio, video, CD-ROM;
- use the means of communication available to the student, providing oral interaction, such as telephone, videoconferences, voice chat, etc

It should be noted that the strategies to be learned must be repeatedly presented to students, commented on, compared, evaluated. The use of strategies may have different degrees of independence.

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